

SELF-REFLECTIVE LEARNING OF TEACHER EDUCATORS FOR DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHING PROFESSION

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Abstract

This paper is mainly focused on self-reflective learning of teacher educators. In it meaning of teacher educator and self reflective learner is explained. The different components of a cycle of reflective learning are discussed in brief. The probable areas for teacher educators are given for applying the process of self-reflective learning. Finally the role of teacher educator in reflective learning is discussed.

Introduction

The profession of education is mint for human development among all other profession. Education is rooted in human conscious is supreme and therefore development of educational process is supreme. It includes creative, hardworking, honest teacher as an important factor, but teacher education prepared honest, skilled, capable and dedicated teachers. Thus the teacher educators play the key role for this purpose.

Reflective teaching is a thoughtful insight of teaching assumptions, predictions, objectives, methods, content and result before, during and after the actual teaching, a reflective journey from reflections of technical, contextual level to its dialectical level. For this purpose the teacher educator must be a self- reflective learner.

Teacher Educator

A teacher educator is one who is a scholar with expertise in the discipline of education and also in the teaching partitioning with competency in the profession of teaching. It is capable for enabling student teachers how to learn from education as a liberal subject as well as a profession and blend both for transforming them to human engineers. It also imparts knowledge and builds skills and thereby transforms those practicing-teachers to teacher-practitioners.

Self-Reflective Learner

For updating and growing the knowledge in the area of teaching-learning practices and professional development, the teacher educators mainly require to learn ‘how to learn’ selfly and develop zest for continuous self learning through reflection. Eraut (1994) opined that ‘ a professional needs first to become professional learner in order to become learning professional.’

According to Beaty (1998), Self –reflection is a systematic approach to learn through four distinct stages within a cycle of experience and reflection along with generalizations and testing. But in the process it too involves consultancy beyond reflection.

The cycle of self reflective learning is presented diagrammatically as—

FIGURE: A Cycle of Self-Reflective Learning

Experience:

Experience is the foundation that develops curiosity in the professionals to reflect upon and learn further leading to self satisfaction and transform himself/ herself from a professional learner to a learning professional.

Experience that breads effective teachers is the stepping stone to reflective learning. As this approach is concerned, the teacher educator reflects on the experiences in the form of teaching tasks performed and practices carried out. Building of knowledge through habits, styles, tendencies, books, journals, seminars, conferences, workshops, field experiences, direct experiences, discussions etc. is the fundamental aspects to the development of their professional practice.

Reflection:

Reflection indicates self brain storming based on evidences gathered through experiences. What are my strengths? What are my weaknesses? Why these weaknesses? Can I able to improve it? Can I minimize by myself or by the help of others? Is there any good practice of mine? Why this practice is so effective?

Generalizations:

Generalizations can be made on the basis of reflection and consultancy. Generalizations requires Self-belief, deeper thoughts, ability to draw precise and accurate inferences. Find out the probable reasons of my weaknesses? How can I discard these weaknesses and converts into the area of my strengths?

Testing:

Testing followed by generalizations, testing encourages for a searching of solutions of problems, improvement of performance, better and proper utilization of skills through education and training.

Learning:

To conclude the teacher educator more effective than the earlier, it is necessary to test the generalizations. It gives a sense of self-satisfaction, personal happiness, and scope to look for further education and training as learning professional.

It reveals that professional development cannot be gained easily without meaningful efforts. It requires open, free and enquiring mind for how to make learning. Reflection does not automatically flow from experiences or learning from reflection through consultancy, generalizations, testing. Conscious and meaningful efforts can yield effective learning and provide a base of further education and training in the cycle.

Areas for applying the Model of Self-Reflective Learning by Teacher Educators

1. Learning experiences provided in the classroom were adequate, precise and effective?
2. Can I use the teaching aids properly?
3. Can there is a adequate co-ordination between my teaching and use of teaching aids?
4. Can I address the class by considering the heterogeneous nature of class?
5. Can I follow the Pedagogy?
6. Can student-teachers enjoy my classes?
7. Can my teaching style in tune with the learning style of student-teachers?
8. Can I check the student-teachers lesson plans properly?
9. Can student-teachers take care of my earlier suggestions in delivering the present lesson?
10. Can I observe the lessons of student-teachers according to norms of observation?
11. Can I become a better teacher educator than what I was earlier?
12. Which values I exhibit in my action in and around the classroom and the institution?
13. What does the institution expect from me where I serve?
14. Am I effective to develop teaching skills among student-teachers for teaching profession?
15. Is my potential to perform as teacher-educator same like the previous year?

Role of Teacher Educator

Teacher Educator must use their own resources initially than the external resources in the areas of content, methodology, pedagogy, process, techniques of teaching-learning process.

The teacher educator should be well acquainted to perform the different tasks—

1. Making classroom teaching more interactional than mere instructional, more participative than mere receptive, more discussional than dictatorial.
2. Procuring the information to transform and create knowledge.
3. Communicating the better and effective ideas.
4. Perform various activities in collaboration with team members.
5. Should access Net for collecting update references.
6. Should use approaches like multimedia and virtual classroom for teaching.
7. Enrichment of subject content.
8. Developing self instructional materials for learning.
9. Developing good achievement tests.
10. Peace-oriented attitude, beliefs and values.
11. Entrepreneurship in life.
12. Providing consultancy for conducting and evaluating research projects.

Conclusion

To develop professional development among teacher educators, the effective strategy is the self learning and developing professionalism through self-reflective learning.

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